

STORAGE OPTIMIZATION BY HOLISTIC BY APPROACH IN SELF-BALANCING E-VEHICLE

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ABSTRACT:

Today's market offers a variety of E-Bikes, since the production of electrical vehicles is expanding quickly to address the lack of fuel efficiency of internal combustion engines. The primary goal of the Our project is to develop self-balancing electric vehicles that use gyroscopic technology to increase stability and safety. In order to decrease the vehicle's weight and hence boost its efficiency, space optimization is necessary. In order to do this, we are optimization storage in self-balancing vehicles by taking into account both user and vehicle design constraints through a holistic approach. to create a new chassis model based on an optimized design that ensures the vehicle is stable and effective.

Keywords: chassis design, storage optimization, self-balancing, and gyroscopic technology.

INTRODUCTION

Optimizing storage in electric vehicle (EV) with a holistic approach involves several aspects, multi-Dimensional Optimization, system-Level integration, Efficiency improvement and optimized frame design etc...

In this research, a holistic approach is proposed for storage optimization in self-balancing E-Vehicle design considering external and internal parts of the body as design variables. All related disciplines, including structure, stability and effectiveness are considered. By reducing the weight of the vehicle we can increase the efficiency, by considering these principles we are using holistic approach to achieve the maximum efficiency, for that we are designing new chassis model using CATIA V5, and analyzed different stress points. The optimal configurations are evaluated in various aspects. The resulted optimal configurations have meet all design objectives and constraints.

A holistic approach to storage optimization in electric vehicles involves considering the entire system and its various components in an integrated manner. It goes beyond individual aspects and takes into account the interactions and dependencies among different elements of the electric-vehicle (EV) ecosystem.

I. LITERATURE REVIEW

When designing an electric scooter chassis with a holistic approach focused on storage optimization, the goal is to ensure that all components are efficiently arranged to maximize space while maintaining performance and safety. This involves considering the integration of battery packs, motors, electrical systems, and storage compartments to create a balanced and user-friendly design. While designing a electric scooter chassis we have to consider certain aspects efficient battery placement, built in storage compartments, aesthetic and environment conversations, safety and stability.

While focusing on storage optimization, it's essential to maintain an perfect design that appeals to users. A sleek, minimalist design can be achieved by integrating components seamlessly into the chassis, reducing visible clutter. Environmental considerations are also important, with an emphasis on sustainable materials and manufacturing practices that reduce waste and energy consumption.

Safety should never be compromised in the pursuit of storage optimization. The chassis design must ensure structural integrity and stability under various conditions, such as different terrains and weights. Consider incorporating features like suspension systems, anti-lock brakes, and safety reinforcements to maintain a high level of safety while achieving storage efficiency.

Biswal, Bibhuti. (2021). Design And Development Of Electric Scooter He added that the chassis is an important feature of the scooter because it serves as the structural foundation for all other components. Structural steel was employed due of its great strength and lightweight properties. This project aims to create and construct a lightweight battery-powered E-Scooter using a BLDC hub motor gearbox system. Which has a load carrying capacity of 100 kg and a speed of 60 kmph..

kenjikaarita, , created an aluminium chassis. The frame's material is AISI 1018. They employed the variable section extrusion method to construct the chassis. It was created with the help of computer-aided engineering. Aluminium material has the benefit of weight reduction According to the authors of this study, the aluminium chassis meets the weight reduction, strength, and stiffness targets. They also agreed that the remaining technical concerns will be addressed, allowing commercial deployment of the aluminium frame.

Alireza Arab Solghar, Zeinab Arsalanloo The Hyundai Cruz Minibus chassis was tested and analysed. Modelling and simulation were carried out using ABAQUS software. Static analysis considers the chassis's self-weight, whereas dynamic analysis considers acceleration, braking, and road roughness It was found that the strains on the chassis induced by braking were greater than those caused by acceleration.

Structural Analysis and Optimization of E-Scooter Chassis Frames:

This study by Zhang et al. (2019) conducted a comprehensive structural analysis of e-scooter chassis frames using finite element analysis (FEA). The research focused on optimizing the frame geometry and material selection to enhance structural rigidity while minimizing weight

Optimization of E-Scooter Chassis Frames for Crashworthiness:

Li and Chen (2021) investigated crashworthiness optimization techniques for e-scooter chassis frames. The study utilized numerical simulations and experimental validation to enhance frame designs for improved energy absorption and occupant safety during collision events.

Topology Optimization of E-Scooter Chassis Frames for Weight Reduction:

Zhang and Wang (2021) employed topology optimization methods to redesign e-scooter chassis frames for weight reduction while maintaining structural integrity. The study utilized advanced optimization algorithms to generate optimized frame geometries based on specified design constraints and performance objectives

Roslan Abd Rahman (2008) utilised FEM stress analysis to provide preliminary data for fatigue life prediction. They employed ABAQUS software for simulation and analysis, as well as ASTM Low Alloy Steel AISI 1018 for investigation. The primary goal was to identify the highly pressured location where Fatigue Failure would begin..

II. OBJECTIVES:

- 1. Develop a Comprehensive Understanding:** Gain a deep understanding of the current state-of-the-art in storage optimization techniques and chassis design principles for self-balancing e-vehicles through literature review and research.
- 2. Optimize special configuration:** the holistic optimized approach are advanced special techniques to minimizes the vehicle weight while maximizing usable spaces, and improving the performance and vehicle efficiency.
- 3. Design and Model a Holistic Storage Optimization System:** Develop a holistic storage optimization system for a self-balancing e-vehicle, taking into account factors such as Gyroscope and battery placement, weight distribution, and structural integrity.
- 4. Conduct Finite Element Analysis (FEA):** Utilize finite element analysis (FEA) techniques to model and analyze the structural performance of the scooter chassis under various loading conditions, ensuring optimal strength and durability.
- 5. Optimize Storage Configuration:** Implement optimization algorithms to optimize the storage configuration of the self-balancing e-vehicle, aiming to maximize storage capacity, improve energy efficiency, and enhance vehicle performance.

III. DESIGNING OF CHASSIS USING CATIA V5:

- i. INTRODUCTION TO CATIA:** Computer-Aided Three-Dimensional Interactive Application (CATIA).

3D Interactive Application (CATIA). CATIA is mechanical design software. It is a feature-based, parametric solid modeling design tool that takes advantage of the easy-to-learn Windows graphical user interface. You can create fully associative 3-D solid models with or without constraints while utilizing automatic or user-defined relations to capture design intent.

Fig: CATIA LOGO

ii. CHASSIS DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS:

Sl.no	Description	Dimensions
1.	Wheel base	1524 mm
2.	Overall Length	1551 mm
3.	Height between wheel axle and ground	165 mm
4.	The height between the pivot of the rear absorber and ground	211 mm
5.	The height between the Rear end of the main frame and ground	745 mm
6.	The height between the Absorber head of the front forks and ground	421 mm
7.	The height between the Steering bearing and ground	645 mm
8.	The height between the joint of the handlebar and ground	745 mm
9.	The height between the Outer siders of the handler and ground	800 mm
10.	The included angle between the axle center line of the front absorber and the perpendicular	28° mm

iii. **SKETCHING OF CHASSIS:** We designed a sketch by using Catia v5 software with the required dimensions for storage optimization in self-balancing e-vehicle by using the following commands:

- Line • Point • Axis • Arc • Circle • Trim
- Spline • Symmetry • Plane • Join • Constrain •

iv. **MODELLING OF CHASSIS:** We designed a model by using Catia v5 software with the required dimensions for storage optimization in self-balancing e-vehicle by using the following commands:

- Pad • Pocket • Symmetry • Rib • Pattern

SECTIONAL VIEWS

IV. ANALYSIS OF CHASSIS USING CATIA V5:

Finite Element Analysis (FEA) in CATIA V5: Finite Element Analysis (FEA) in CATIA V5 provides engineers and designers with a powerful suite of tools for simulating and analyzing the structural, thermal, and dynamic behavior of their designs. From preprocessing to postprocessing, CATIA V5 offers seamless integration, allowing users to prepare CAD models, define boundary conditions, create finite element meshes, and visualize results efficiently. With its integrated solver, CATIA V5 performs numerical computations to simulate displacements, stresses, temperatures, and natural frequencies accurately. The versatility of CATIA V5's FEA capabilities makes it indispensable across industries, enabling users to validate designs, optimize performance, and ensure compliance with industry standards, ultimately contributing to the reliability and safety of products.

i. Displacement Analysis:

- Displacement analysis calculates the deformation of a structure under applied loads.
- Users define boundary conditions, loads, and material properties for the model.
- CATIA V5's FEA capabilities solve the system of equations derived from the finite element mesh to determine the displacement field.
- Results include the magnitude and direction of displacement at each node in the finite element mesh.
- Engineers use displacement analysis to ensure that the deformation of the structure remains within acceptable limits and to identify areas of potential failure or excessive deformation.

Displacement Analysis

ii. Stress Analysis:

- Stress analysis evaluates the distribution of internal forces (stresses) within a structure under applied loads.
- Users define boundary conditions, loads, and material properties, similar to displacement analysis.
- CATIA V5's FEA solver calculates stresses based on the finite element mesh and material behavior.
- Results include von Mises stress, principal stresses, and stress concentrations.
- Engineers use stress analysis to assess the structural integrity of components, identify potential failure modes, and optimize designs to withstand operating conditions.

Stress Analysis**iii. Precision Analysis:**

- Precision analysis in CATIA V5 involves assessing the accuracy and reliability of geometric models and assemblies.
- It helps verify dimensional accuracy, tolerances, and fit of components within an assembly.
- CATIA V5 provides tools for analyzing clearances, interferences, and deviations from nominal dimensions.
- Engineers use precision analysis to ensure that parts and assemblies meet design requirements and functional specifications

Precision Analysis

V. MATERIAL SELECTION

- Mild Steel

Why mild steel

Mild steel, also known as low-carbon steel, is a type of carbon steel that contains a relatively low carbon content, usually between 0.05% and 0.25%. It is known for its malleability, ductility, and ease of welding. These properties make it widely used in various industries, including construction, automotive, and manufacturing.

- **Strength:** Mild steel provides good structural strength, allowing it to withstand impacts and support heavy loads.
- **Weldability:** Due to its low carbon content, mild steel is easy to weld, making it suitable for fabrication and assembly.
- **Cost-Effectiveness:** Mild steel is generally less expensive than other metals like aluminum and carbon fiber, making it an economical choice.
- **Availability:** Mild steel is widely available, ensuring consistent supply for production and maintenance.

Mild steel's combination of strength, ductility, weldability, and cost-effectiveness makes it a versatile material with many applications. However, its weight and corrosion vulnerability can be significant drawbacks, especially for applications like electric scooter chassis where lightness and corrosion resistance are crucial. Protective coatings and careful design can mitigate these limitations, making mild steel a suitable choice for specific applications.

However, mild steel has some notable limitations. Its weight is significantly higher than other materials commonly used in electric scooter chassis, such as aluminum alloys, carbon fiber, and magnesium alloys. This added weight can impact the scooter's performance, including speed, battery life, and maneuverability, making it less suitable for high-performance or lightweight scooters. Additionally, mild steel is prone to rust and corrosion, necessitating protective coatings or regular maintenance to ensure long-term durability, especially in outdoor environments.

VI. MATERIAL PROPERTIES:

PROPERTIES	MATERIAL	
	ALUMINIUM ALLOY	MILD STEEL
Density (kg/m ³)	2660	7850
Elastic modulus (MPa)	70,300	210,000
Poisson's Ratio	0.3	0.3
Yield Stress (MPa)	125	250
Ultimate strength (MPa)	275	360
Design Stress (MPa)	93.75	176.25
Weldment Strength (MPa)	100	200
Weldment Design Strength (MPa)	75	141

VII.METHODOLOGY

Optimizing storage utilization in electric scooters requires a holistic approach that considers both design and functionality. Here are some methodologies to optimize storage utilization in electric scooters:

- **Space-Efficient Battery Placement:**

Optimize the placement of the battery and power components to ensure they do not occupy excessive space. Consider innovative solutions such as integrating the battery into the frame or using compact, high-capacity batteries.

- **Efficient Use of Frame and Chassis:**

Utilize the frame and chassis efficiently to integrate components and storage features. Avoid oversized components that do not contribute significantly to functionality.

- **Lightweight Materials:**

Explore lightweight yet durable materials to minimize the overall weight of the scooter. This can contribute to improved energy efficiency and better performance.

- **Smart Storage Solutions:**

Incorporate smart storage solutions that utilize space more efficiently. This could involve foldable or expandable storage compartments that can adapt to varying storage needs.

- **Multi-Functional Components:**

Design components with multiple functions to maximize utility. For example, integrating a seat with built-in storage or a battery compartment can serve dual purposes without sacrificing space.

- **Integrated Technology:**

Integrate technology seamlessly into the scooter design to avoid bulky add-ons. For instance, consider embedding charging ports, connectivity features, and navigation systems directly into the scooter's frame.

- **Optimized Frame Design:**

Streamline the scooter's frame design to eliminate unnecessary voids or wasted spaces. This involves careful consideration of the overall shape and structure to maximize storage potential.

- **User-Centric Storage Solutions:**

Design storage solutions based on user needs and behavior. Conduct user surveys and feedback sessions to understand the types of items users typically carry and optimize storage accordingly.

VIII. RESULT TABLE

SPECIFICATIONS	MINIMUM	MAXIMUM
Total Deformation	0mm	13mm
Von-Mises Stress	0.00MPa	227.97MPa
Principles Stresses	-402.1MPa	253.3MPa

IX. CONCLUSION:

This project is mainly focus on design the chassis for self-balancing, aiming to enhance their efficiency, range, and overall performance. The electric scooter chassis design not only provide better strength but also better component mounting. The design analysis on chassis carried different loads and impacts the design has carrying the maximum load **120kg i.e1190N and minimum load 60kg**

X. REFERENCES:

- (i) 'Solid Modeling' By A.A.G., And Voelcker: A Historical Summary and Contemporary Assessment IEEE Computer Graphics and Applications vol.2, March 1982
- (ii) DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF ELECTRIC BIKE By B. Sushma, Amith, G, Akhileshwer Reddy, 'International Journal of Trend on Scientific Research and Development 2019'
- (iii) Michel Ashby, Elsevier, Material Selection in Mechanical Design.
- (iv) Pullivan, Inc: 'CAD/CAM Market in The United States' report 15664,
- (v) Mahesh Gowda Patil, B Ravindra, H S Manjunath, Stress and Strain Analysis Of Weldment Of Rectangular Column Structure, In 2018